

Synthesis and Fungitoxicity of Some 2-Thiohalogeno-Nitrophenyl-Benzimidazoles

S. P. GUPTA and (Miss) SARITA RANI

Department of Chemistry, D. N. College, Meerut.

Manuscript received 9 August 1976; accepted 30 December 1976

Seventeen 2-thio-halogenonitrophenyl-benzimidazoles have been prepared by the condensation of halogenonitrobenzenes and sodium salt of 2-mercaptobenzimidazole. They have been characterised and tested for their antifungal activity against *Alternaria tenuis*, *Helminthosporium sativum*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Fusarium oxysporum* by spore germination method. A relation between fungitoxicity and structure has also been established.

BENZIMIDAZOLE derivatives with substituents such as amino, nitro, chloro, mercapto when present at position 4 or 6 have been found to possess inhibitory effect on the development of certain viruses¹. Woolley² observed that benzimidazole inhibited the growth of several yeasts and bacteria. Various benzimidazoles are effective inhibitors of the growth of yeasts, lactobacilli³, vaccinia virus⁴ and influenza virus¹. Recently Rebstock et al^{5,6}, reported that several acid analogs of 2-mercaptobenzimidazole arrested leaf and stem growth of cranberry, bean plants and root formation of cucumber seedlings. In view of previous observations^{7,8} that halogens and nitro groups considerably enhance the biological activity of organic molecules, we report the synthesis and fungitoxicity of some 2-thio-halogenonitrophenyl-benzimidazoles.

2-Thio-(2, 4-dinitrophenyl)-benzimidazoles (III) have been obtained by refluxing equimolecular quantities of different halogenonitrobenzenes (II) with the sodium salt of 2-mercapto-benzimidazole⁹ (I) in ethanolic solution (vide Table). The I. R. spectra of these compounds have also been recorded and are in complete agreement with their structures.

These compounds were tested for their antifungal activity against *Alternaria tenuis*, *Helminthosporium sativum*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Fusarium oxysporum*

by spore germination method¹⁰ (Table-I). The percentage inhibition of the spores at 10 ppm have been recorded.

Experimental

2-Mercaptobenzimidazole⁹. A mixture of 32.4 gms. (0.3 mole) of *o*-phenylene diamine, 52.8 gms (0.33 mole) of potassium ethyl xanthate, 300 ml. of 95% ethanol and 45 ml of water was refluxed for 3 hours in a one litre flask. Norit (12 gms) was then added cautiously, and the mixture was again heated for 10 minutes at the reflux temperature. Norit was removed by filtration. The filtrate was heated to 60-70° and treated with 300 ml of warm tap water (60-70°) followed by 25 ml of acetic acid dissolved in 50 ml of water with good stirring. The product separated as glistening white crystals. It was recrystallised from 95% alcohol, m.p. 303-04° yield 85%.

2-Thio-halogenonitroaryl-benzimidazoles :

An alkaline solution of 2-mercaptobenzimidazole (0.01 ml.), in absolute alcohol (20.0 ml) and aqueous caustic soda (0.01 ml) in water (4.0 ml) was treated with a solution of halogenopolynitrobenzene (0.01 mole) in absolute alcohol (20 ml). The mixture was refluxed on water bath for about an hour and filtered. The hot filtrate on cooling gave crystals of 2-thio-halogenonitroaryl-benzimidazoles in almost quantitative yield. These were recrystallised from absolute alcohol.

The benzimidazole derivatives so prepared are insoluble in water but completely soluble in absolute alcohol. Their melting points, yield, analytical data and fungitoxicity have been recorded in Table-I.

Structure of Some 2-thio-halogenonitrophenyl-benzimidazoles :

Sodium salt of 2-mercaptobenzimidazole on condensation with 1, 2, 4-trichloro-3, 5-dinitrobenzene (IV) having two labile chlorine atoms in position-2 and -4

TABLE I— 2-THIO-HALOGENONITROPHENYL-BENZIMIDAZOLES

S. No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	% Nitrogen		% Sulphur		Percentage inhibition of spores at 10 ppm.			
					Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	AT	HS	AN	FO
1.	2,4-DNP	180	95	C ₁₈ H ₈ N ₄ O ₄ S	17.69	17.72	10.07	10.12	28	30	36	40
2.	2,6-DNP	213	85	C ₁₈ H ₈ N ₄ O ₄ S	17.67	17.72	10.09	10.12	30	34	28	42
3.	2,4,6-TNP	200	78	C ₁₈ H ₇ N ₄ O ₄ S	19.41	19.39	8.89	8.86	38	40	42	50
4.	2-Chloro-4,6-DNP	215	90	C ₁₃ H ₇ ClN ₄ O ₄ S	15.97	15.97	9.15	9.13	50	33	44	26
5.	2-Bromo-4,6-DNP	210	85	C ₁₃ H ₇ BrN ₄ O ₄ S	14.13	14.17	8.07	8.10	25	27	20	10
6.	3-Chloro-4,6-DNP	185	95	C ₁₃ H ₇ ClN ₄ O ₄ S	15.95	15.97	9.05	9.13	18	21	18	26
7.	4-Chloro-2,6-DNP	156	80	C ₁₃ H ₇ ClN ₄ O ₄ S	15.95	15.97	9.06	9.13	36	28	25	30
8.	2-Methyl-4,6-DNP	245	90	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₄ S	16.94	16.97	9.68	9.69	20	10	28	00
9.	4-Methyl-2,6-TNP	220	70	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₄ S	16.92	16.97	9.74	9.69	21	10	10	38
10.	3-Methyl-2,4,6-DNP	285	80	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₄ O ₄ S	18.65	18.66	8.50	8.53	05	08	05	04
11.	2,3-Dichloro-4,6-DNP	100	85	C ₁₃ H ₆ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₄ S	14.57	14.54	8.27	8.31	23	25	30	28
12.	2,4-Dichloro-3,5-DNP	145	65	C ₁₃ H ₆ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₄ S	14.58	14.54	8.28	8.31	15	24	18	28
13.	2-Chloro-4-Bromo-3,5-DNP	95	78	C ₁₃ H ₆ ClBrN ₄ O ₄ S	11.72	11.81	6.70	6.75	12	18	10	15
14.	2-Chloro-3-bromo-4,6-DNP	86	70	C ₁₃ H ₆ ClBrN ₄ O ₄ S	12.97	13.04	7.43	7.45	18	12	8	5
15.	2-Chloro-5-methyl-4,6-DNP	230	95	C ₁₄ H ₉ ClN ₄ O ₄ S	15.31	15.36	8.72	8.77	20	15	4	0
16.	2-Bromo-5-methyl-4,6-DNP	225	90	C ₁₄ H ₉ BrN ₄ O ₄ S	13.67	13.69	7.80	7.82	6	13	0	0
17.	3-Chloro-2-methyl-4,6-DNP	116	78	C ₁₄ H ₉ ClN ₄ O ₄ S	15.35	15.36	8.74	8.77	24	32	28	12

DNP and TNP refers to dinitro and trinitrophenyl respectively. All melting points are uncorrected. Satisfactory C, H analysis have been obtained for all these compounds.

AN, AT, HS, FO refers to *Aspergillus niger*, *Alternaria tenuis*, *Helminthosporium sativum* and *Fusarium oxysporum* respectively.

can possibly give two isomeric products, 2-thio-(2, 5-dichloro-4, 6-dinitrophenyl) - benzimidazole (V) and 2-thio-(3, 4-dichloro-2, 6-dinitrophenyl)-benzimidazole (VI) respectively. From the reaction mixture only one compound could be isolated, which is identical with the compound obtained by the condensation of 1-bromo-2, 5-dichloro-4, 6-dinitrobenzene (VII) and sodium salt of 2-mercaptobenzimidazole. Both of them must, therefore, be 2-thio-(2, 5-dichloro-4, 6-dinitrophenyl)-benzimidazole.

Similarly, 1, 2-dichloro-4-bromo-3, 5-dinitrobenzene on condensation with sodium salt of 2-mercaptobenzimidazole can possibly give two isomeric products, 2-thio-(2-chloro-5-bromo-4, 6-dinitrophenyl)-benzimidazole and 2-thio-(3, 4-dichloro-2, 6-dinitrophenyl)-benzimidazole respectively. From the reaction mixture however only one compound could be isolated, which is identical with the compound obtained by the condensation of 2, 4-dibromo-1-chloro-3, 5-dinitrobenzene and sodium salt of 2-mercaptobenzimidazole. Both of them must, therefore, be 2-thio-(2-chloro-5-bromo-4, 6-dinitrophenyl)-benzimidazole.

Results and Discussion

2-thio-halogeno-polynitroaryl benzimidazoles have been found to possess marked fungitoxicity at 10 ppm level. The addition of nitro group at ortho or para position to the sulphide linkage considerably enhance fungitoxicity. A halogen atom increases fungitoxicity when placed at the ortho or para position to the sul-

phide linkage. However, a halogen atom at the meta position seems to decrease it. A methyl group when present in nitrophenyl ring decreases fungitoxicity to a larger extent.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of Junior fellowship to one of them (S.R.). Thanks are also due to Dr. R. S. Kapil, C.D.R.I., Lucknow for providing spectroscopic and microanalysis data.

References

1. I. TAMM and K. FOLKERS, *J. Exp. Med.*, 1953, **98**, 245 ; *J. Bact.*, 1956, **72**, 54, 59.
2. D. W. WOOLLEY, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1944, **152**, 225.
3. D. HENDLIN and M. H. SOARS, *J. Bact.*, 1951, **62**, 633.
4. R. L. THOMPSON, *J. Immunol.*, 1947, **55**, 345.
5. T. L. REBSTOCK, C. D. BALL, C. L. HAMMER and H. M. SELL, *Plant Physiol.*, 1955, **30**, 382.
6. REBSTOCK et al., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 5831.
7. S. P. GUPTA and (Miss) PREM DUREJA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, Vol. L, 546.
8. S. P. GUPTA and (Miss) PREM DUREJA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, Vol. LI, 936.
9. J. A. VAN ALLAN and B. D. DEACON, *Organic Synthesis*, Volume, IV, p. 569.
10. F. WILCOXAN and S. E. A. MCCALLAN, *Can. Boyce. Thomp. Inst.*, 1939, **10**, 329.